

STATUS OF RESISTANCE AGAINST SPOT BLOTCH IN WHEAT

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Introduction

Wheat crops produced in warm, humid climates suffer significant production losses due to spot blotch. Spot blotch has been a severe impediment in wheat output over the past four decades, not just in north India's Eastern Gangetic Plains (EGP), but also in Bangladesh, Nepal, Brazil, and other nations. Spot blotch affects an estimated 25 million hectares of wheat land worldwide (van Ginkel & Rajaram, 1998), with roughly 40% of that produced on the Indian subcontinent (Joshi *et al.*, 2007a), where crop losses due to spot blotch are estimated to be in the 15–25% range (Dubin & van Ginkel, 1991). The causal organism *Bipolaris sorokiniana* colonises the older leaves at the base of the wheat plant before moving up to the canopy's upper level (Joshi *et al.*, 2002). Crop management, soil fertility, planting density, plant developmental stage, and meteorological conditions encountered by the host throughout later stages of the life cycle all influence disease severity (Joshi *et al.*, 2007b).

Fig. 1: The mode of infection and the disease cycle of *Bipolaris sorokiniana* causing spot blotch in wheat (Gupta *et al.*, 2018)

High relative humidity favors infection and pathogen proliferation by allowing the canopy to stay moist for an extended length of time (Acharya *et al.*, 2011). The disease spreads in the Indian subcontinent when the temperature remains above 26 °C (Chaurasia *et al.*, 2000), which explains why late-sown wheat is particularly susceptible (Duveiller *et al.*, 2005). Spot blotch and terminal heat stress are common causes of productivity loss in the Indian EGP, Nepal, and Bangladesh, where wheat is traditionally planted following the harvest of the preceding rice crop (Joshi *et al.*, 2007c).

Symptoms: Small light brown lesions, generally oval to rectangular to slightly elliptical in form, approximately 5–10 mm long and 3–5 mm broad, develop on the leaf, sheath, node, and glumes as spot blotch symptoms. These brown-margined lesions can be seen all over the leaves and eventually grow in size and merge to create bigger necrotic areas (reaching several centimetres). Chlorophyll deficiency develops quickly in the damaged leaves, and they finally perish. The spikes are also impacted in the most extreme circumstances, and a dark brown to black discoloration around the seed's germinating point, known as 'black point,' emerges. Several abiotic elements, such as soil quality, moisture, and temperature, influence the disease's severity.

Breeding for spot blotch resistance

Conventional breeding- BH1146, a moderately resistant Brazilian cultivar, was originally a significant source of resistance, although other significant sources of resistance became available later (e.g., Yangmai 6 and Ning 8201). Synthetic wheats containing the D genome of *Aegilops tauschii* (the parent of the D genome of bread wheat) have also been used to increase resistance, as shown by cv. Chirya 3 (Mujeeb Kazi *et al.*, 1996). Through shuttle breeding and multilocation screening in multiple stress nurseries, a number of recently released high-yielding wheat varieties with spot blotch resistance have been produced (Joshi *et al.*, 2007c). It's also been discovered that lesion mimic loci (*Lm/lm*), which are responsible for the spontaneous production of necrotic patches on leaves and confer rust resistance, increase the risk of spot blotch. As a result, in those wheat-growing regions of South Asia where rust is not yet an issue, the inclusion of these *Lm* loci in spot blotch resistant genotypes should be avoided (Pandey *et al.*, 2016). Where rust and spot blotch are both an issue, the use of *Lm/lm* for rust protection must be done with caution.

Molecular breeding- Because a significant number of markers linked with a number of genes/QTL for spot blotch resistance are now available, pyramiding of more than one gene for spot blotch resistance will be a favoured technique. *Sb1*, *Sb2*, and *Sb3* may all be transmitted via backcrossing programmes and pyramided using related markers, as has been done effectively for the production of rice cultivars resistant to bacterial blight (BB) and blast diseases (Guvvala *et al.*, 2013; Arunakumari *et al.*, 2016; Ellur *et al.*, 2016). Spot blotch resistance appears to be quantitative, thus, these three genes, as well as other minor QTL, can be transferred via marker-assisted recurrent selection (MARS), which entails numerous cycles of selection and intercrossing among the chosen plants harbouring one or more genes/QTL. Another strategy that might be beneficial in the future is genomic selection without the use of marker-trait connections (since each accessible marker is thought to be connected with a major or minor gene/QTL).

Conclusion

Spot blotch of wheat is still a major problem in hot, humid places of the world, such as Southeast Asia. Despite tremendous advances in understanding the biology of *B. sorokiniana*, as well as cultural practises that may be employed to mitigate yield losses caused by this disease, this is the case. Although certain resistance QTL/genes have been found and resistant cultivars created, none of these cultivars are totally resistant since resistance is quantitative in nature and regulated by polygenes, each of which has a little influence. To comprehend the host–pathogen interaction and determine if a gene-for-gene link exists, researchers must do both fundamental and applied research to uncover *avr* genes in the pathogen and the matching resistance genes in the host.

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